

Deliverable 2.2

Report on Large awareness and public engagement event

@biovoices

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1. Executive Summary

The Transition2bio project builds upon the most relevant communication and education EU-funded projects and initiatives to contribute to the implementation of the updated 2018 EU Bioeconomy Strategy and promote the transition towards more sustainable production, consumption, and lifestyles by implementing an integrated package of activities addressing a wide range of target stakeholders.

In the frame of the **Task 2.1 Large-scale awareness and public engagement events**, led by PEDAL at least **6 large-scale awareness and public engagement events should be organized in 6 EU countries** (IT, BE, PT, SK, GR, DE) (reaching at least **40.000 people**) to **increase the target stakeholders' knowledge and awareness of the potential benefits of all sectors of bioeconomy**.

The organisation of the events will be **based on the successful format of the “Bioeconomy Village” and the BioART Gallery** implemented in BIOWAYS and BIOVOICES, displaying the bio-based products in everyday situations, enabling the visitors to touch and feel what bio-based economy is. This format was implemented in several large-scale international exhibitions throughout the last three years (Maker Faire; Researchers' Night; the updated Bioeconomy Strategy launch event; “Science is Wonderful”; “Bioeconomy scene”; “BBI-JU Stakeholder Forum”, etc.), reaching more than 100.000 people in total.

Despite the challenges related to the COVID-19 pandemic and the restrictions resulting in postponing or cancelling several events, **the Transition2bio project managed to organize 4 large scale events in 2021, reaching more than 18.000 participants**. However, due to the COVID-related restrictions in place, the number of visitors was reduced considerably in the case of all events, which is also reflected in the number of persons reached by the Transition2bio events:

- *Traditions of the Slovak countryside* in August 2021 in Slovakia, reaching more than 800 participants.
- *Science in Game – Super Researchers for Planet's Future* in September 2021 in Italy, reaching more than 300 participants.
- *European Researchers' Night* in September 2021 in Italy, reaching more than 400 participants.
- *Maker Faire – The European Edition* in October 2021 in Italy, reaching more than 7000 participants.
- *Geco for school* - an online educational platform providing Italian secondary schools and students with educational modules related to sustainability, reaching 10 000 participants.

The following sections provide an overview of the large-scale events where the Transition2bio project took part during the 2021. **Section 3** is focused on the event held in Nitra. **Section 4** dives into the activities and material used during the *Science in Game – Super Researchers for Planet's Future*. In **section 5**, an overview of *the European Researchers' Night* in Frascati. While, in **section 6**, the participation in the *Maker Faire – The European Edition*. **Section 7** will present a resume of the Transition2bio booth impact on the audience. Followed by **section 8**, where all the lessons

learnt during the event are collected. Finally, in **section 9** a table will show the plan for the next period, listing the future events where the Transition2bio booth will take part.

2. Introduction

Transition2bio is a 24-month Coordination and Support Action project that aims to promote the transition to a more sustainable production, consumption, and lifestyle by means of the Bioeconomy, contributing to the implementation of the updated 2018 European Bioeconomy Strategy. The project will build upon the results of the most relevant communication and education EU-funded projects and initiatives and implement an integrated package of communication, awareness-raising and educational activities, while actively engaging the wider public, Member States and Regions on the one hand, and expanding the European Bioeconomy Network¹ and furthering its activities.

More specifically, the strategic objectives of the Transition2bio project are defined as follows:

- Valorise and exploit sectoral communication tools and activities developed at national, regional, and local levels by EU-funded Bioeconomy projects and other relevant initiatives.
- Raise awareness on the Bioeconomy and its related environmental and socio-economic impact on European citizens through a range of communication activities.
- Contribute to the transition to a more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle through engagement and educational activities.
- Contribute to the deployment of the regional Bioeconomy strategies by providing Member States and Regions with methodologies, mentoring, capacity building, tools and materials to raise awareness of and communicate the Bioeconomy.
- Facilitate the identification of the educational and training needs in view of creating an innovative ecosystem for the Bioeconomy.
- Strengthen the European Bioeconomy Network to maximise the collaboration among EU-funded Bioeconomy projects and their collective impact.

Those strategic objectives are to be implemented through the main activities of the project, which focus on:

- Collecting available awareness-raising, communication and educational material deriving from relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives to be put at the wider public's disposal through the creation of an online library. The material will also be organised in the form of toolkits tailored to the needs of the stakeholders identified and targeted by the project, namely:
 - the DEMAND side (i.e., the general public with particular attention being paid to children and teenagers, students and young researchers, public procurers interested in adopting sustainable and/or bio-based solutions at national, regional and local levels, etc.);
 - the SUPPLY side (i.e., the primary sector, Bio-based industries, SMEs and large enterprises, etc.);

¹ The European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet) is a proactive alliance of EU-funded projects promoting, communicating and supporting the bioeconomy through knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, and coordination of joint activities and events.

- MULTIPLIERS AND SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT (i.e., Citizens' organisations, NGOs and other associations, brands, retailers, educators, influencers, the media, policy makers, public authorities at national, regional and local levels, networks and clusters, etc.).
- Interacting with the wider public during large-scale awareness raising events, placing great emphasis on children and teenagers through hands-on labs, info-educational games, and school competitions, with teacher training being a key component.
- Supporting Member States and Regions in the implementation of awareness and communication activities for the design and deployment of their Bioeconomy Strategies by providing them with mentoring, mutual learning and bioeconomy-related capacity building activities.
- Identifying future skills needed for the Bioeconomy and the related educational needs.
- Expanding the European Bioeconomy Network by attracting new relevant partners (e.g., BBI-JU, BIC, the SCAR Bioeconomy Strategic Working Group, the BIOEAST Initiative, etc.) and animating the collaboration among them to consolidate and reinforce the existing synergies, maximise opportunities and the impact of bioeconomy promotional activities.

This deliverable aims to:

- Provide an overview of the Large-scale awareness and public engagement events organized by Transition2bio in the 1st year of the project;
- Share the experience of partners with implementing the strategy to maximise the impact of the events as described in the D2.1;
- Summarize the lessons learnt and provide recommendations for organization of future events.

3. Background

Within the Transition2bio project, six (6) large-scale events² will be organised in 6 EU countries (IT, BE, PT, SK, GR, DE) reaching at least 40.000 participants and each target group defined by the project (DEMAND, SUPPLY and MULTIPLIERS/SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT). These activities will be organised in the context of large events already attracting thousands of participants addressing topics like sustainability, green lifestyles, science and innovation, citizen science, etc.

To ensure that the expected number of large-scale events is organised, and the target groups and desired number of participants are reached, an online future events calendar was developed.

Due to the COVID-19 preventive measures, several events identified in the preparation phase were cancelled or postponed. Therefore, mitigation measures have been proposed by the respective partners. Nevertheless, during 2021, the Transition2bio project took part in five (5) large-scale events. Four of them were held in Italy and one in Slovakia.

Figure 1: Transition2bio roll-up in the context of the Maker Faire – The European Edition

3.1 Concept, formats, and materials

The organisation of the events is based on the successful format of the “Bioeconomy Village” and the BioART Gallery implemented in BIOWAYS and BIOVOICES, displaying the bio-based products in everyday situations, enabling the visitors to touch and feel what bio-based economy

² In general, large-scale events can be described as complex events attended by a large number of visitors, taking place over multiple days and/or locations – e.g., conferences, fairs, exhibitions and professional seminars.

is. This format was implemented in several large-scale international exhibitions (Maker Faire; Researchers' Night; the updated Bioeconomy Strategy launch event; "Science is Wonderful"; "Bioeconomy scene"; "BBI-JU Stakeholder Forum", etc.), reaching more than 100.000 people in total.

3.1.1 The Bioeconomy Village format

The **Bioeconomy Village** concept was developed initially in the context of the BIOWAYS, promoting the showcase of bio-based products in everyday's life applications, enabling the visitors to touch and feel the bioeconomy.

Figure 2: The Bioeconomy Village at the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

What is the bioeconomy? What bio-based products do we use in our everyday lives? Can we make more sustainable choices for the environment and our health? The BIOECONOMY Village aims to raise awareness, improve knowledge on products of renewable origin and promote the applications and benefits of Bioeconomy, the circular economy and sustainability, fostering dialogue, confrontation and sharing between the general public, researchers and companies.

Through the display of products, examples, and practical demonstrations, visitors are shown, in a clear and engaging way, how the bioeconomy is increasingly part of our daily lives and how conscious consumer choices can have a positive impact on the environment, society and the economy.

The exhibition is continuously enriched with new products, and it is composed of more than 350 different bio-based products.

Figure 3: Informative roll-ups surrounding the Bioeconomy Village

The Village is usually accompanied by pictures, posters, as well as innovative tools such as games (serious games, video games and quizzes), videos, Fact sheets and other materials.

3.1.2 The BioART Gallery format

The **BioART gallery** is a powerful tool to attract interest, raise awareness, inspire, and stimulate curiosity and discussion. Agriculture, cosmetics and nutraceuticals; construction and restoration, cleaning and hygiene; design and clothing; toys and sporting goods are just some of the sectors where the circular bioeconomy can have a positive impact on the environment, society and economy.

Figure 4: The Bio-ART gallery at the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

The BioART gallery consists of several types of visual materials that can be selected according to the type of event and context (maxi pictures, standalone cardboard panels or roll ups), which have high visual impact, showcasing and explaining several sustainable circular bioeconomy applications and products. The BioART gallery covers all bioeconomy sectors.

The BioART Gallery presents promising feedstock and its related bioeconomy applications in everyday life. It offers an innovative approach of showcasing to the public some examples of bio-based products and applications currently available in the market through several examples.

Figure 5: The Bio-ART gallery

The **online BioART Gallery** - An interactive digital slideshow where users can navigate through all surprising bio-based applications identified through a simple click.

3.1.3 The „What's bioeconomy” book for kids

Strengthening the knowledge and sensitivity of future generations to environmental issues, sustainability and circularity through information and education programmes targeting the younger generation can contribute to raising future citizens, decision-makers and workforce, informed and interested in bioeconomy.

To tackle these challenges, the **book "What's bioeconomy"** was developed in the frame of the European funded project BIOVOICES (HORIZON 2020 - biovoices.eu/book/concept/) and it is the first book ever written for kids on the sustainable and circular bioeconomy.

It is targeted to young people at pre-school and primary school in order to increase awareness of the environmental, social and economic benefits of the bioeconomy and its sectors, in particular bio-based sectors.

The book for kids illustrates a story of a family (mum, dad, grandmother and four siblings) living in the world of the sustainable and circular bioeconomy, a world where everyone has a sustainable way of life, knows that waste is a treasure, where something new can come out from what is usually wasted. Ben and Bea, the older brother and sister of the family, welcome the young readers in their world.

Figure 6: The bioeconomy book for kids “What’s Bioeconomy?”

This book promotes scientific sound contents in an easy and comprehensive way and has been validated by a Scientific Committee involving 33 high level experts covering all the bioeconomy sectors, from academia and industry, representing several European countries. The authors of the book are Chiara Pocaterra (APRE) and Susanna Albertini (FVA) and the illustrator is Alistar Illustration (alistarillustration.com)

The book is formed by eight scenes:

1. Five everyday scenarios
 - a. House
 - b. School
 - c. Countryside
 - d. Seaside
 - e. City - Park – Supermarket
2. Two transversal pages, to better understand some key elements of bioeconomy
 - a. Bioeconomy world
 - b. Glossary

The book has been translated in 11 languages (Italian, Portuguese, Spanish, Greek, Dutch, German, Romanian, Slovak, Estonian, Hungarian, French) and printed in 15.000 copies that has been already distributed in selected schools, bookshops, museums for children and institutional contexts around Europe. It is also available online at this [link](#).

During the events, many copies of the book were disseminated to targeted visitors.

For more information, see the Deliverable 2.4.

3.1.4 Factsheets, videos and other materials

Factsheet, or in other words documents providing detailed information about bioeconomy, biobased products or services can be displayed during events. Factsheets, such as the "[Suitcase of products](#)" created in the BLOOM project. They can be used as an additional source of information for visitors. Factsheets on various topics related to bioeconomy were developed in several projects.

Videos, such as "[The bioeconomy in our everyday lives](#)" created by the BIOWAYS project, allow for more efficient processing and memory recall. The video, available in seven languages, presents some fascinating facts about the bioeconomy.

Transition2bio has developed an [online library](#) to make available in a transparent, readily available, user-friendly and visual-attractive way all the contents, materials and tools identified and collected from at least 100 different sources.

4. Traditions of the Slovak countryside (Tradície slovenského vidieka)

In Slovakia, Transition2bio participated in a three-day open-air event held from 19th to 22nd of August 2021 called *Traditions of the Slovak countryside (Tradície slovenského vidieka)* in Nitra.

The representative partner of the event was PEDAL in partnership with the [Slovak Bioeconomy Cluster](#).

Figure 7: The Transition2bio booth during the Traditions of the Slovak countryside in Nitra

4.1 Before the event

4.1.1 The organisation of the booth

The *Traditions of the Slovak countryside* event was the most challenging to organise because of the uncertainties related to the COVID-19 situation. The international exhibition was cancelled, and the organization of a smaller-scale national event was confirmed just three weeks before the starting date. The event was originally designed as an indoor event, but due to the anti-epidemic measures had to be changed and re-designed to an open-air exhibition.

Figure 8: Visitors at the Transition2bio booth during the Traditions of the Slovak countryside in Nitra

4.1.2 The promotion

In the frame of the *Traditions of the Slovak countryside* event, the promotion strategy aiming to create “AHA moments” and to show potential visitors the added value of the Transition2bio booth for focused on the following channels:

- PEDAL-Consulting Facebook page. Four posts were published in the weeks before the event. In Figure 4 it is possible to see an example.
- PEDAL-Consulting LinkedIn page. The account published four posts in Slovak to promote the participation of the Transition2bio project in the event in Nitra, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 9: Promotion post on PEDAL Consulting’s Facebook and LinkedIn account related to the Traditions of the Slovak countryside event in Nitra

Figure 10: Promotion post on PEDAL Consulting’s LinkedIn account related to the Traditions of the Slovak Countryside event in Nitra

4.2 During the event

4.2.1 The target audience reached

The entries were limited due to the National COVID-19 rules. Even though the number of attendees was reduced and the impact of the Transition2bio booth was less than the expectations, in the three days, the Transition2bio exhibition attracted more than 800 visitors.

4.2.2 The Booth

In the context of the event in Nitra, the Transition2bio booth was located outside as shown in the Figure 9 below. To create the right atmosphere for inspiring and learning and to ensure enough space and visibility to the materials, the stand was divided in several parts.

Figure 11: Visitors exploring the different sections of the Transition2bio booth during the Traditions of the Slovak countryside in Nitra

4.2.3 Informational materials

During the *Traditions of the Slovak countryside* event several informational materials were displayed in the booth. The roll-ups taken from the [BioArt Gallery](#) project realized by BIOVOICES along with leaflets worked as support to explain bioeconomy and its benefits. Posters showed examples of bio-based products, presenting them as alternatives to less sustainable products and showing their applications in everyday life.

4.2.4 The Bioeconomy Book for Kids

In the four days of the event, the printed copies of the book for kids “What’s Bioeconomy” was displayed on the tables of the booth to attract visitors and to start a discussion on Bioeconomy and the scope of the Transition2bio project.

Around one hundred (100) printed copies of the book were distributed to teachers and families. Kids had to answer a simple quiz on bioeconomy before receiving their free copies.

Figure 12: Kids with the Bioeconomy Book “What’s Bioeconomy?” at the Transition2bio booth during the Traditions of the Slovak countryside in Nitra

4.2.5 Bio-based samples

In the Transition2bio booth several bio-based products were displayed. Among the others, insulation materials made from hemp, bamboo-based dress and pot, socks made from waste of the coffee production and wood-based bags.

Figure 13: Biobased products in the Transition2bio booth at the Traditions of the Slovak countryside in Nitra

4.2.6 The activities

All activities were designed so as to communicate the key messages (What is bioeconomy? What are the benefits of bioeconomy? Bioeconomy in our everyday lives). In order to target all groups (demand, supply side and general public including kids, several activities were planned, including quizzes, experiments, presentation of product and material samples, and provision of information.

As the visitors of the event were mainly families with children, a short quiz was prepared with the aim to provide an introduction and basic knowledge of bioeconomy in a form suitable for children. The experiments selected from the "book for kids" and the Transition2bio deliverable D2.1 included the wind catcher, the coffee scrub, the disinfectant, and the biogas factory. In both cases, adults were actively participating in the activities, contributing to the discussions.

In the *Traditions of the Slovak countryside*, online games and videos were used but the visitors' interest for them was limited in the frames of an open air event. As for the TV, there was too much light, and it was not possible to watch the video. Therefore, although videos are a powerful tool, their use in open air events should be carefully planned, taking into consideration the equipment available and setting of the booth.

The organization of experiments, quizzes and hands-on lab activities required respecting the COVID-19. It was necessary to sanitize the tools and the materials necessary for the experiment on each repetition.

Figure 14: Experiments with kids during the Traditions of the Slovak countryside event in Nitra

4.2.7 Collaboration

In the frame of the *Traditions of the Slovak countryside*, a sample of bio-based coffee cup created an occasion of collaboration with a coffee shop, and it represented an indirect way to attract visitors to the Transition2bio booth. The PEDAL team shared some compostable coffee cups with the coffee shops to increase awareness among its customers and to attract visitors that wanted to discover more about bioeconomy.

Figure 15: The coffee shop with Bio-based coffee cups during the Traditions of the Slovak countryside event in Nitra

4.2.8 Promotion

To attract visitors, to retain their attention and to increase the impact of the booth among the audience, the staff actively invited people to the Transition2bio stand. They offered giveaways, like edible cups as incentives to visit the booth with successful results.

The book for kids and memory game, offered as giveaways for those who participated in the quiz, were an excellent way to invite the families with kids to the booth.

Figure 16: The Transition2bio booth during the Traditions of the Slovak countryside in Nitra

5. Science in Game – Super Researchers for planet Future

The event *Science in Game – Super Researchers for Planet Future* took place in the framework of *Cartiera Latina*, a former paper mill in the *Appia Antica Regional Park* in Rome the 19th of September 2021.

The Transition2bio representative was FVA, and the event was organized in collaboration with [Frascati Scienza](#). The *Science in Game – Super Researchers for Planet Future* was the launching [event](#) of the EU researchers' night and it was dedicated to LEAF, (heal thE pLANet's Future).

5.1 Before the event

5.1.1 The organisation of the booth

During the event, the visitors could explore four worlds inspired by video games: BiodiversiLand, the Zero-Pollution Castle, the Climate Change Cave, and the Kingdom of Circular Economy where the Transition2bio booth was located. The aim of the event was to raise awareness and to increase knowledge about bioeconomy through the exhibition and explanation of bio-based products.

By respecting safety measures in relation to COVID-19, the personnel took care of the cleaning of disinfection and the organisation of the event was straightforward. The planned structure was confirmed without any meaningful difference.

Figure 17: The Transition2bio booth during the *Science in Game – super researchers for planet's future* in Frascati

5.1.2 The promotion

To promote the participation of the project to the event and to show the added value of the Transition2bio booth to the potential participant, FVA used the following channels:

- The BIOVOICES' Facebook account. Six posts were published in the weeks before the event in Italian as shown in Figure 14.

- The FVA official website. Before the event, FVA posted two articles ([1](#) and [2](#)) on its website in Italian.
- The BIOVOICES and FVA’s Twitter account. Two posts were published in the weeks before the event on social media.
- European Researchers’ Night Channels
- Frascati Scienza channels

Figure 18: Promotional post on Biovoices’ Facebook account related to Science in Game – Super Researchers for Planet Future in Frascati

5.2 During the event

5.2.1 The target audience reached

During the day, more than three hundred (300) visitors explore the stand, mainly young people. Many primary schools participated in the event for a total of 150 kids and the Transition2bio booth.

5.2.2 The booth

The Transition2bio exhibition booth was composed of four tables, two of them dedicated to hands-on activities, experiments and games and two to the biobased products exhibition.

The live event was a good setting to test and get feedback about the book for kids “What’s Bioeconomy” with teachers and families.

5.2.3 Bio-based samples exhibition

Even if the exhibition of the bio-based samples was time and energy consuming and risky due to the pandemic restriction, it was amazingly effective in attracting visitors to the booth. Curiosities and storytelling starting from bio-based products are useful to inspire and engage participants into a discussion. Questions like “Is this product sustainable?” or “Is it really compostable?” and “What is its impact on the environment?” arose thanks to the bio-based products. Starting from the most funny and intriguing samples (for instance paper made from

animal poop) is extremely effective with the younger audience and increases the interactivity of the explanation.

Figure 19: Exhibition and explanation of the bio-based samples during the Science in Game – Super researcher for planet future in Frascati

5.2.4 The Bioeconomy Book for kids

The event was the occasion to distribute seventy-five (75) printed copies of the Book for kids “What’s Bioeconomy”. The book was distributed not only to teachers and kids but also to teachers and other already popular scientific promoters to increase the impact of the Transition2bio project.

5.2.5 The activities

Coupling the booth with hands-on activities helped to create a dynamic environment and to attract more visitors to the booth. The labs attracted kids, and it worked as a driver to invite them to see the bio-based materials and to learn more about bioeconomy in general.

In addition, teachers, parents and other visitors were engaged in explanations and discussions about the bio-based products and the bioeconomy. It should be noted that several questions demonstrating a good awareness maturity were collected, like questions about impacts, sustainability, processes, etc.

Finally, the involvement of a high school student enabled the Transition2bio team to test the format From Students2Students, where peer education is promoted (see D2.4 for details).

Figure 20: Kids exploring the Transition2bio booth during the Science in Game – Super Researcher for Planet Future in Frascati

5.2.6 Problems faced

This event was the first live event after the COVID-19 limitations. The kids were enthusiastically participating in all the suggested activities.

Nevertheless, the organisation of these interactive activities, although it was openair, everybody was wearing masks and the FVA personnel were continuously disinfecting the materials, was too crowded for the period.

Therefore, after this event, we decided to drastically limit physical contacts and hands on activities. A hybrid solution was successfully experimented in Researcher's Night, while for Maker Faire, since the faire was much more crowded, it was decided to avoid any risk.

6. The European Researchers' Night

The *European Researchers' Night* took place at Scuderie Aldobrandini in Frascati from 23rd to 24th of September 2021. The Transition2bio representatives were FVA and APRE and it was organized in partnership with [Frascati Scienza](#). The Scuderie Aldobrandini is an historic building connected to the Tuscolano Museum.

6.1 Before the event

6.1.1 The organisation of the booth

In the context of *European Researchers' Night*, FVA and APRE presented the Bioeconomy Village with hands-on demonstration and bio-based product exhibition. The planned structure under the title "Discover the Bioeconomy" was confirmed without meaningful differences.

Figure 21: The Transition2bio booth during the European Researchers' Night in Frascati

6.1.2 The activities

In the frame of the *European Researchers' Night*, the Bioeconomy Village coupled hands-on demonstration and bio-based products exhibition. During the second day of the event, the booth hosted the 2021's winners of the Bioeconomy Prize, assigned in the context of the [Startupper School Academy](#) organized by [Lazioinnova](#).

6.1.3 The promotion

Both APRE and FVA actively promoted the participation of the Transition2bio booth in the weeks before the event to attract potential visitors. Below the list of the channels used by the two partners. The event was also extensively promoted through the researcher's night channels and through Frascati Scienza channels:

- BIOVOICES and APRE Facebook account. Both pages promoted the event with eight posts as shown in Figure 22.
- FVA and APRE official websites. Both partners posted articles for the promotion of the event on their websites ([1](#), [2](#) and [3](#)).

- FVA and APRE Twitter account. Potential participants could find three Tweets promoting the event in Frascati.
- European Researchers' Night Channels
- Frascati Scienza channels

Figure 22: Promotion post on BIOVOICES' Facebook account related to the European Researchers' night in Frascati

6.2 During the event

6.2.1 The target audience reached

By respecting the safety measures related to COVID-19, the booth attracted more than four hundred (400) visitors during the two-day exhibition. The public participating at the event was heterogeneous, although extremely active and engaged in the activities proposed by the Transition2bio project.

Figure 23: Visitors during the European Researchers' Night in Frascati

6.2.2 The booth

In the context of the *European Researchers' Night*, the Bioeconomy Village was located indoor in the ancient Scuderie Aldobrandini Buildings.

Transition2bio exhibition area included the BioArt Gallery, three tables, one for the experiments, and two for the bio-based products exhibition. A space was allocated to host the student winners of the Bioeconomy Prize of the Startupper School Academy (see D2.4 for details).

A TV touch screen was used to make available the online gamified version of the book for kids.

Figure 24: Visitors discovering the Transition2bio booth during the European Researchers' Night in Frascati

6.2.3 The informational materials

The booth was surrounded by the [BioArt Gallery](#) project's roll-ups. They worked as supporting materials for the explanation of different feedstock and its related bioeconomy applications in everyday life. The roll-ups gave a figurative support to effectively lead the explanation. From their examples, through storytelling and curiosities, it was possible to inspire and engage participants into a discussion.

Figure 25: Informational materials and bio-based product from the Transition2bio project

6.2.4 The activities

Although the number of students allowed to enter simultaneously in the exhibition area was limited, the organisation of hands-on labs hosting, in the same table more than 10 kids, was qualified by the organisers (FVA and APRE) as too risky in times of COVID-19. Therefore, it was decided to couple the booth with live experiments, conducted by a scientist. The kids were actively participating by responding to questions and supporting the scientist as vice-researchers but were requested to not touch the materials for safety reasons. These activities facilitated the creation of a dynamic environment and to attract more visitors to visit the rest of the booth, working as a driver to invite them to see the bio-based materials and to learn more about bioeconomy in general.

In addition, teachers, parents, and other visitors were engaged in explanations and discussions about the bio-based products and the bioeconomy.

6.2.5 The Bioeconomy Book for kids

The Transition2bio booth displayed several printed copies of the Bioeconomy book for kids “What’s Bioeconomy?”. APRE and FVA distributed 150 copies in Italian to teachers and families. Leaflets and QR codes advertised the open access version of the book sharing the link to discover it.

The touch screen with the online gamified version of the book was highly appreciated by kids and teachers. Printed posters with the QR code of the game were displayed in several areas of the exhibition space to promote the use of this version both from kids and teachers in their schools.

6.2.6 Bio-based samples exhibition

The booth exhibited many bio-based samples and products. Those worked perfectly as a teaser to inspire and engage visitors into a discussion about bioeconomy, its benefits and applications and the scope of the Transition2bio project. Moreover, the bio-based products offered the possibility to deepen the analysis with more technical details, related to the brands currently delivering bio-based goods, the cost of this type of products and the real possibility to integrate them into the daily routine.

6Figure 26: Bio-based products and samples in the Transition2bio booth during the European Researchers' Night in Frascati

6.2.7 Hosting the winners of the Bioeconomy Prize of the Startupper School Academy

During the second day of the European Researchers' Night, the Transition2bio stand hosted the winners of the Bioeconomy Prize assigned in the context of the Startupper School academy organized by Lazio Innova. The winning team (Engine4You) realized a project consisting of hemp-based disposable masks and a hemp-based brick, produced directly with the masks after their disposal.

The students were directly involved in the explanation of their project and the Student2students format was extremely effective to engage the younger audience. Moreover, the presence of the school project in the booth helped to increase the interest about possible application of bioeconomy approach also in the educational environment and to see the impact that a bottom-up initiative could reach, opening to further research and applications.

Figure 27: The presentation of the winning project of the Startupper School Academy during the ERN event in Frascati

The winners of the Bioeconomy Prize of the Startupper School Academy were enthusiastic about the experience, which provided them a great stage to present their project and get feedback from the real public.

7. Maker Faire – The European Edition

The *Maker Faire – The European Edition* in Rome was a three-day hybrid event from the 8th to 10th of October 2021 held in the Gazometro, an old industrial park in the city of Rome, involving 21 thousand people. It should be noted that the 2020 edition was held only online. The previous editions counted 130.000 visitors. This year, the public authorities significantly limited the number of people allowed to enter each hour, as well as the number of personnel allowed per each exhibition area.

The Transition2bio representatives were FVA, APRE and PEDAL and the event was organized in partnership with [Innova Camera](#). The event was in a hybrid form, with both indoor and outdoor stands. The location of the Transition2bio booth was inside one of the buildings of the location.

7.1 Before the event

7.1.1 The booth

The Transition2bio booth was designed as an installation made by recycled cardboard that reproduced different home settings (the kitchen, the bathroom, and the living room). In each room, visitors could find the bio-based products and samples related to the context.

The Transition2bio booth was surrounded by the [BioArt Gallery](#) roll-ups, covering around 80 square meters.

Figure 28: The Transition2bio booth during the *Maker Faire – The European Edition* in Rome inside the Gazometro

7.1.2 The promotion

The Transition2bio representatives (APRE, FVA and PEDAL) actively promoted the participation of the Bioeconomy Village to the *Maker Faire – The European Edition* during the weeks before the event. The channels used for the promotion are listed below:

- BIOVOICES' Facebook account. Five posts were published in the project's official Facebook page, as shown in Figure 29.
- FVA official website. The partner published two articles to promote the Transition2bio participation in the event ([1](#) and [2](#)).
- FVA and PEDAL Twitter accounts. Partners published seven Tweets to attract visitors.
- Maker Faire channels

Figure 29: Promotion post on BIOVOICES' Facebook account related to the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

7.2 During the event

7.2.1 The audience

The event attracted numerous people and the booth hosted more than 7000 visitors during the three days of exhibition.

Many visitors were innovators (makers) due to the nature of the event, which is dedicated to digital fabrication and innovation in different sectors and areas. Nevertheless, most of the public was generic, but science/technology passionate and highly interested in bioeconomy.

Figure 30: Visitors exploring the Bioeconomy Village during the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

7.2.2 The booth

The Transition2bio booth representing a home, allowed visitors to find the bio-based products and samples that can be found in our house (in the kitchen, the bathroom, and the living room).

This setting allowed them to discover those goods in their “natural” environment and to understand that bioeconomy is a reality, and they can find advice and ideas to introduce some of the products in their daily lives. The installation was extremely effective in attracting visitors during the three days.

Figure 31: The recycled cardboard installation representing the living room and bathroom during the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

7.2.3 The informational materials

The Transition2bio booth was surrounded by the [BioArt Gallery](#) roll-ups in Italian. Those enhance the visual impact of the stand creating the perfect frame for the cardboard installation. By displaying some examples of bio-based products and applications currently available on the market, the roll-ups worked as visual support to engage the audience into a discussion and explain bioeconomy and the scope of the Transition2bio project.

Figure 32: The BioArt Gallery project's roll-ups during the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

7.2.4 The activities

During the event, the Transition2bio booth exhibited the bio-based products; those worked as effective examples to explain bioeconomy and its applications currently available on the market.

Figure 33: Explaining biobased products in everyday's applications during the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

Due to the nature of the event and considering the amount of expected audience, no hands-on labs or practical demonstration were organized during the event, to avoid health risks due to COVID-19 emergency.

7.2.5 The Bioeconomy Book for kids

During the *Maker Faire – The European Edition*, the booth displayed printed copies of the Bioeconomy Books for kids "What's Bioeconomy". The event was the occasion to distribute one

hundred twenty-five (125) books in Italian and twenty-five (25) copies in English to teachers, journalists, and museums. Unfortunately, the project doesn't have enough copies to be

distributed to all the kids that requested it. To solve this question, kids and families received the link to discover the open access online version of the book thanks to many leaflets and QR codes distributed in the booth. Finally, at the end of the event, the partners collected direct contacts (e.g., email address) of teachers and educators interested in the Transition2bio activities.

Figure 34: Kids exploring the BIOECONOMY book for kids “What’s Bioeconomy”

7.2.6 Bio-based samples Exhibition

More than 350 samples of bio-based products and materials were displayed in the Transition2bio booth divided into three sections. In the kitchen, visitors could discover the different applications of bio-based materials in disposable dishes and cutlery along with many nutraceutical products. In the bathroom, bamboo-based toothbrushes, cosmetics and detergents. Finally, samples of bio-based textiles and papers were displayed in the living room. The recycled cardboard installation offered the ideal context for the bio-based materials increasing the attractiveness of the Transition2bio booth.

7.2.7 Promotion of the @biovoices social media channels

During the Maker Faire – The European Edition, visitors were invited to take a picture inside the Bioeconomy Village and to post it with the hashtag #Biovoices.

Moreover, the visitors could find leaflets and small cards with the link to the project’s social media pages on the tables of the stand and all around the installation.

Figure 35: Leaflets in the Bioeconomy Village during the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

7.2.8 Hosting the winners of the Bioeconomy Prize of the Startupper School Academy

Even at Maker Faire, the Transition2bio exhibition space hosted the winners of the Bioeconomy Prize assigned in the context of the Startupper School academy organized by Lazio Innova. The participants were directly involved in the explanation of the winning project. Moreover, the presence of the school project in the booth helped to increase the interest about possible application of bioeconomy approach also in the educational environment and to see the impact that a bottom-up initiative could reach, opening to further research and applications.

Figure 36: Representatives of the winning team at the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome

8. GECO for school

“[Geco for school](#)” is an online educational platform providing Italian secondary schools and students with educational modules related to sustainability.

Figure 37: The Geco for school portal

This initiative was launched for the first time in 2021 and Transition2bio partner FVA was contacted to contribute by providing contents related to the circular bioeconomy.

This experience is a very good example of how effective it could be to enter as a partner in already existing initiatives that will take care of the logistics, the involvement of participants, the promotion, etc., while Transition2bio provides the contents to be delivered to the participants.

8.1 Before the event

8.1.1 Contents definition

Geco for schools guides the visiting students in virtual travel in the sustainability world, by providing educational experiences in different topics connected to green deal and sustainability. The topics covered by Geco for schools are:

- Eco-food
- Circular Economy
- Renewable energies
- Green Mobility
- Sustainable Tourism

In this context the preparatory phase was mainly connected to the definition of the contents to be prepared for the training module "What's Circular Bioeconomy?", to be delivered under the section "Circular Economy".

Figure 38: A screenshot of the Geco for school virtual campus

8.1.2 Contents delivery

Once agreed on the contents, the training sessions have been produced, in form of pre-recorded videos:

- an interview highlighting the main concepts of the circular bioeconomy, the connection with the circular economy, the main application fields, the impacts of the society, the economy and the environment
- a video to explain the bioeconomy by showcasing several bio-based products.

Figure 39: A moment from the "What's Circular Bioeconomy?" course: the interview

Similar to the physical events, the concept for this course was inspired by the Bioeconomy village and BioART gallery. The idea was to provide several examples, from different application fields of the circular bioeconomy and, starting from them, to provide educational contents and inspirational insights for the future careers of the students. The training module is available on this [link](#).

8.2 During the event

8.2.1 The audience

The educational exhibition was open for the classes from October to December 2021. According to the organizers, about 10.000 students participated in the course.

8.2.2 How it works

The schools participating in the initiative can enter the platform on a pre-booked date and can freely explore the virtual space, using their personal 3D avatar. Several events are available, including live interaction and a series of educational content. At the end of the day, they should have attended all the training modules and can complete the online gamified self-assessment session. Based on the scores, the best students can win educational prizes, made available by the project's partners.

Figure 40: The video course about bioeconomy and bio-based products

8.2.3 Awarding the participants

Transition2bio made available to the winners of the circular bioeconomy session some bio-based gadgets and a 2-hour webinar to deepen the contents related to the bioeconomy topics.

The award phase will take place in late December 2021 or early January 2022.

8.3 Considerations

Although this activity has a strong educational dimension and targets the young people, the format can be considered a large-scale event. In addition, the Transition2bio cannot be considered the main provider of the educational experience, that covers a wider perspective.

For these reasons it was reported in this deliverable.

9. Impact on the Audience

Engaging the public is necessary to increase the impact of the Transition2bio project during the large-scale events and it is crucial for creating the inspiring and educational atmosphere inside the booth. In the five events where the Transition2bio project took part more than 18.000 people visited the booth deepening their knowledge about bioeconomy and increasing their awareness on bio-based products. The formats of Bioeconomy Village, Bio-Art Gallery, the book for kids and experiments created based on the book, were very successful in the events.

9.1 The audience

Following the recommendations of the D2.1, it is important to understand the segments of the public present during the event (demand, supply or multipliers). The demand side was the primary target of the events, while multipliers and the supply side were less represented among the visitors.

- During the *Traditions of the Slovak Countryside*, thirty representatives of the Civil society and business sector attended the event and visited the Transition2bio booth.
- The *Science in Game – Super Researchers for Planet Future* and the European Researchers Night events were directed to families and teachers.
- In the *Maker Faire – The European Edition*, the majority of visitors were young people, generic public, innovators and teachers due to the nature of the event.
- *Geco for school*, provides information to students and teachers about the bioeconomy via an online platform.

Figure 41: The audience during the *Science in Game – Super Researchers for Planet Future* event in Frascati

9.2 Engagement and feedback

The collection of feedback is crucial to understand the reaction of the audience and to improve the Transition2bio booth and activities. Feedback helps to enhance the organisation of the large-scale events to provide a fun, inspiring and educational experience to the visitors.

The public was very enthusiastic and interested in the topic of bioeconomy, bio-based products, feedstocks and any technical details related to compostability and biodegradability of the goods.

In the five events, the visitors agreed on the importance of raising awareness about bio-based products and Bioeconomy among the society. Most of them expressed the will to know more about the brands exhibited in the booth to buy their bio-based products and increase the sustainability of their purchasing habits.

In the *Tradition of the Slovak Countryside*, the visitors focused on the importance of finding systemic solutions and creating markets for sustainable products (either by governments or by companies themselves); many of them saw it as crucial point in ensuring wider use of bio-based goods.

The organization of experiments, quizzes and hands-on labs activities were a good way to attract kids. These initiatives worked very well with the younger audience, and it was possible to actively engage kids increasing their knowledge on bioeconomy and, at the same time starting a discussion with parents or tutors. More information is available in D2.4.

The collection of feedback was oral, the personnel present in the booth directly asked to the public for impressions and comments about the Transition2bio project and its related activities. In the following chapter, a summary of the feedback collected during the five events, divided by public segment.

9.3 Demand

9.3.1 Young people

Young people showed enthusiasm and interest in learning Bioeconomy, they were ready to take on the challenge of finding new and sustainable ways of living. During the events, they were actively engaged in discovering and exploring the bio-based samples and in making experiments, games, and quizzes. The materials developed in Transition2bio/BIOVOICES are extremely helpful to interact with kids and to explain the basic concepts of bioeconomy.

Figure 42: Kids playing with the online game during the *Tradition of the Slovak Countryside* event in Nitra

9.3.2 General Public

The general public showed great interest in deepening their questions and their basic knowledge on Bioeconomy and sustainability. Most of them showed some knowledge about the bio-based products and some of them already used them in their daily life.

Samples were the main way to attract families and they were a good starting point for a conversation on bio-based products. Many visitors asked for technical information related to the samples (time for biodegradability/compostability of goods, sustainability of the life cycle of the products); this highlights the importance of having well prepared personnel at the booth to provide satisfactory and precise answers. Also, they were interested in the availability of such products in their respective countries and asking about local producers of bio-based products.

Other visitors were interested in the challenges related to accessibility of bio-based products in terms of price and availability in “standard” shops. The group of parents agreed on the importance of future training and educational activities targeting kids and youth.

Figure 43: The audience during the Maker Faire – The European Edition event in Rome

9.4 Multipliers and supportive environment

9.4.1 Journalists

Journalists asked for copies of books, and they were extremely interested in writing articles on the project and the Bioeconomy challenges. The events were an occasion to start collaboration with the press to increase the impact of Transition2bio activities. Transition2bio personnel was interviewed during the events by the media.

9.4.2 Civil society

During the *Tradition of the Slovak Countryside*, fifteen representatives of Civil society visited the booth. They considered very positively the use of samples and bio-based products, defining it as

inspirational. They also started a discussion on how to include sustainability/bioeconomy in their activity through information, training, and workshops for participants.

9.4.3 Researchers

Few researchers visited the booth during the *Tradition of the Slovak Countryside* and the *European Researchers' Night*. They provided positive feedback on the project activities and results; they highlighted the importance of such awareness raising activities.

In both Researchers' Night and Maker Faire the researchers were numerous and very interested in the topic. Some of them visited the booth and several future collaborations were discussed. Some samples of BBPs to enrich the Transition2bio exhibition were collected in these events.

9.4.4 Teachers and educators

Teachers were actively present in each event, and they provided very positive feedback on the Transition2bio project.

During the events, teachers were introduced to the Transition2bio project and its main activities. They were extremely curious about the accessibility of the materials (books, quizzes, and memory games), and teachers asked for more informational material (e.g., a dedicated toolkit) about bioeconomy, highlighting the importance of training and education targeting kids and youth.

During the events, the majority of the Bioeconomy Book "What's Bioeconomy?" were distributed to teachers and they provide positive feedback on the educational proposal provided in the frame of the Transition2bio project. The link to the online version was also provided, to be used in the classes that have the digital blackboard (in Italy the majority).

During the Science in Game – Super Researchers for Planet Future event, teachers received information on the online teachers' training.

More than 180 teachers filled the expression of interest form, to be informed of future activities of the project.

Figure 44: Teachers and educators signing the form to receive the BIOECONOMY book for kids during the Maker Faire – The European Edition in Rome.

9.5 Supply

9.5.1 Business

Fifteen business representatives visited the Transition2bio booth during the *Traditions of the Slovak Countryside*.

They asked for information about potential clients and suppliers of bio-based products or bio-based raw materials together with advice and tips on how to promote the bio products.

Also, Maker Faire was a good platform to meet people from the business community, in particular Innovators and StartUPs with ideas in the bioeconomy sector.

Several business-as-usual representatives also asked for information and expressed the idea of being informed on future activities of the project. More than 30 business cards were collected with this aim.

10. Lesson learnt

After evaluation of the completion of five large-scale events during the year 2021, this Deliverable aims to provide insights for future activities. Below it is possible to find a list with some advice, which represents a summary of the experiences, success and mistakes that have turned into lessons learnt.

10.1 Before the event

- In principle, **organizing an exhibition area in the context of large-scale events organized by someone else is always very effective**, because the organisational aspects (promotion, invitation, tickets, logistics, etc.) are covered by the main organizers. This means also the possibility to reach a significantly high number of people, compared to what is possible to reach in an EU funded project. This type of collaboration presents great advantages, but also some constraints: the logistics are partially negotiable, and the spaces can be very expensive. From the extensive experiences gathered in Transition2bio (Researchers' Night, Maker Faire, Geco for School) it is important to prepare a solid value proposition when presenting the request for collaboration. If the event organizers see the value for their final public, often the space is offered under great discount or, in most cases, for free.
- Following the experience during the *Traditions of the Slovak Countryside* event, it is particularly important to **have as much information as possible about the organisation of the event as soon as possible**. This way, organisational risks and uncertainties can be minimised.
- Due to the high level of uncertainty, it is recommended to **design a more flexible concept** of the event that can be easily adjusted to new conditions (e.g., decide about the key message and activities according to the type of event and audience and have a portfolio of tools/materials to be used in different formats).
 - For example, in the case of the *Traditions of the Slovak Countryside* event in Nitra, one set-up was planned if the event took place indoors and another if the event took place outdoors.
- Based on the experience of the Transition2bio project, **awareness raising activities can be organized in various formats and contexts**, e.g., indoor or open-air events, small scale or large-scale events, as well as online events.
- One of the advantages of organising Transition2bio events is the fact that **there is a large amount of high-quality exhibition material, which adapts easily** to different situations and facilitates the preparation of alternative scenarios.

Figure 45: Preparing the Transition2bio booth for the Traditions of the Slovak Countryside in Nitra

10.2 During the event

- The available materials are **flexible enough** to be used in vastly different conditions and locations.
- **Coupling the booth of bio-based products with the architectural environment like the Bioeconomy Village** creates an immersive experience, engaging physically the visitors that can explore the bio-based products in their “natural” context.
 - At the Maker Faire – The European Edition, the Transition2bio booth was in recycled cardboard reproducing a house divided in three areas: the kitchen, the living room, and the bathroom. This design was extremely effective to present the bio-based samples in their environment. The public can better understand that a large part of the bio-based products is already on the market, and it is possible to choose them to make a more responsible choice.
 - It is highly recommended to use samples of products (something to provide a real touch and feel experience) made by local manufacturers, as the audience asks about the origin of the products. Presentation of local products might be a critical point in raising interest in the biobased products.

Figure 46: Engaging and inspiring the visitors of the Transition2bio booth

- **Coupling the booth with the experiments and hands-on lab activities** creates a dynamic environment, attracting visitors and curious, especially young people. The efforts were well paid thanks to the numerous and active participation. In addition, the lack of such activities in the last two years increased the number of participants contributing to the success of the Transition2bio booth.
 - However, in the case of the experiments, quizzes and hands-on lab, the pandemic situation increases the attention and precaution needed to organise and control these activities.
- The **BioArt gallery roll-ups** have a figurative support and effectively lead the explanations on Bioeconomy feedstocks and materials, **absorbing participants into discussions**.
 - However, in the case of open-air events, using TV screens and online games was not successful.
 - The linguistic barriers should always be addressed by translating most of the contents, whenever possible.
- Establishing **collaboration with other exhibitors or other companies** inside the event, providing them bio-based samples is an effective way to attract visitors to the booth.

10.2.1 Tips and advice for the organization of large-scale event

- **Having enough staff in the booth** is crucial to serve all the visitors, which often come in waves, and to answer their questions.
- **Being active and inviting people to the booth**, both with direct and indirect techniques, is extremely effective to attract more participants.
- **Well-trained personnel** are important to answer technical questions. The adult audience is interested in the details related to bio-based products, feedstocks, and end-of-life treatments.

Figure 47: Explaining the Bioeconomy at the Transition2bio booth

- The informative **material is appropriate for the targeted groups**. The adults and high school students are attracted by bio-based samples and informational materials, while kids prefer hands-on lab and other activities. The materials to attract youth are less covered.
- To **engage visitors into a conversation is useful to start from something the visitors already know**, or a **curious anecdote**. In a second moment, introducing technical information is effective with an adult audience, being aware that not every visitor is interested in those details.
- **Stimulating visitors to post pictures and stories on social networks** while visiting the booth tagging @Biovoices increases the visibility of the projects. It enhances social interactions and followers on the Transition2bio social media accounts.
- **Offering teachers additional materials and information** on training is extremely effective in multiplying the impact of the booth and the project.
- The **“From Student2students” format is extremely effective in attracting the younger generation** facilitating the emergence of question and stimulating the conversation.

11. Plan for the next period

Within the Transition2bio project, six (6) large-scale events will be organised in 6 EU countries (IT, BE, PT, SK, GR, DE) reaching at least 40.000 participants and each target group defined by the project (DEMAND, SUPPLY and MULTIPLIERS/SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT).

Despite the COVID-19 pandemic-related restrictions affecting organizing large-scale events faced by the project partners, the Transition2bio project managed to successfully organize five (5) events in 2021, reaching more than 18 000 participants.

An indicative list of large-scale events in which the Transition2bio events might take place in the second year of the project has been created. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic the level of uncertainty remains high, and organization or format of several events has not been confirmed yet. The large-scale events are monitored and the future event calendar is being updated.

Table 1: Future event calendar

Country	Title of the event	Start date
Greece	Agrotica 2022	27/1/2022
Portugal	Planetiers World Gathering	April; October
Portugal	Consumers International Summit	TBC
TBC	EU week of Regions and City 2022	TBC
TBC	EU Green week 2022	TBC
Slovakia	Agrokomplex	TBC

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